

Strong AI vs. Machine Learning for Adding Cognition to Applications – Example in ECommerce

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Machine Learning technologies are becoming increasingly popular as the backbone of building AI applications. However, Machine Learning is just a subset AI -well suited to classification and pattern recognition tasks. Strong AI technologies, based on symbolic reasoning, are also necessary additional components to combine with Machine Learning to build cognitive, more intelligent, applications. An application in ECommerce is used to demonstrate the limitations of Machine Learning and the benefits of leveraging a broader range of symbolic AI technologies to engage users, increase conversion rates and revenue.

2. Aim

To highlight the limitations of Machine Learning technologies, and to demonstrate the benefits of using a broad spectrum of AI methods and tools to build more intelligent applications.

3. Material and methods

Neural Networks, Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees and k-nearest neighbors algorithm are compared with Knowledge-based/Semantic techniques to increase the performance of Search, Recommendations, and User Experience in ECommerce.

4. Results

100 A/B tests were conducted. 50% increase in conversion and 25% increase in average order value were achieved by combining Strong AI techniques with Machine Learning to improve the user experience across 3 different ECommerce web sites.

5. Conclusions

According to our initial test results, combining Machine Learning and Strong AI techniques can significantly increase the performance of Search, Recommendations and User Experience in ECommerce.

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6. Keywords

Neural Networks, Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees and k-nearest neighbors algorithm, Ontologies, Inferencing, Knowledge Representation, ECommerce, User Experience.

Author biography

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